

Analysis of Price, Promotion, and Brand Image on Purchasing Decisions and their Implications for Customer Satisfaction of all Chicken Mart Frozen Food Products

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Abstract:- The purpose of this study is to determine the components that influence purchasing decisions and buyers' dedication to frozen food products. A total of 125 customers of Allchickenmart frozen food store in Cilangkap, East Jakarta, were surveyed using quantitative methods. Using the Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Model (PLS-SEM), information is tested to see how value, progress, and brand image affect purchasing decisions and customer loyalty. This test is expected to provide significant experience for associations in creating a more grounded feature framework.

The results show that brand image and cost affect purchasing decisions and buyer loyalty. Cost affects purchasing decisions but does not affect buyer dependence. While progress does not affect purchasing decisions and buyer loyalty. Purchasing decisions affect customer constancy. The insignificant results are due to dependency factors, such as cost and progress. In line with this, it can be assumed that brand image and cost have a significant role in the buyer's purchase decision, which then, at that point, adds to customer dependence.

Keywords:- Price; Promotion; Brand Image; Purchasing Decision; Customer Satisfaction.

I. INTRODUCTION

Interest in animal protein in Indonesia continues to increase, as seen from the amount of per capita consumption that continues to increase in the period 2018 and 2022. Interest in animal protein products continues to increase, partly driven by population growth and the development of the middle class, which considers increased purchasing power for hamburger products, poultry products, and processed meat and poultry products as a source of protein. Urbanization patterns are also driving interest in processed meat products as city dwellers are generally more accustomed to purchasing meat products that do not require much organization due to their fast-paced lifestyles. Food market utilization in Indonesia is projected to increase during the period 2020-2025E in line with the development of Gross Domestic Product per capita, reflecting increased consumer confidence in the business world. Interest in meat and poultry in Indonesia

shows a positive pattern, given the dominance of the productive age population, the development of the working class and the important role of meat and poultry as a source of animal protein in Indonesia. Research by Nurhuda (2013) shows that wages are one of the elements that generally impact how much animal protein is consumed in Indonesia.

The per capita frozen food usage in Indonesia is projected to increase consistently from 2018, indicating a large room for development of the frozen food market. From 2018 to 2025, frozen food utilization in Indonesia should expand at an annual growth rate of 3.2 percent. The utilization of frozen food products declined in 2021 due to the coronavirus pandemic, but increased again in 2022 and is projected to continue increasing until 2025. Anggraeni et al (2014) stated that increasing consumer interest in frozen food has an impact on increasing interest in chicken and meat.

The rapid development of technology as a promotional tool to increase buying interest and create increased sales of company products, all of which can result in intense competition between businesses as a result of business development. From 2020 to 2022, the monthly sales value of Allchickenmart frozen food stores will fluctuate. This is more due to the purchase design which is influenced by several purchasing factors including the value, progress, and brand of frozen food items from the Allchickenmart store so that exploration is expected to find out the market mix factors that have an impact on the premium in buying frozen food so that it will affect the business value of the Allchickenmart frozen food store.

Therefore, the rationale of this study is to determine the variables that influence buyers' need fulfillment and purchase choices of frozen food products. This exploratory goal of examining the effects of value, progress, and brand image on purchase decisions and, as a result, customer loyalty is one of the objectives of this study. The results of this study are expected to provide significant information for the association in developing a better promotional framework.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Marketing Mix

Kotler and Armstrong (2013) say that the business marketing mix is a collection of tools used to get the desired response from the target market. Tjiptono (2008) defines the marketing mix as a device that helps companies determine the quality of administration to clients, with techniques divided into 4Ps: product, price, place, and promotion (Kotler and Keller, 2013). The marketing mix consists of elements such as product, price, distribution, and promotion, plays an important role in marketing management and helps companies plan effective marketing strategies. The suitability of the marketing mix to market conditions, technological developments, changes in consumer behavior, and global competition is the key to achieving competitive advantage and corporate marketing goals.

B. Price

Price is one of the main components of the advertising mix and can influence customer purchasing choices. Tjiptono (2015) characterizes price as a trade measure that can be equated with cash for the benefits obtained from an item or service under certain circumstances. Susilo and Harini (2018) define cost as how much cash a buyer has to pay to get a decent or administration. Putra et al (2017) characterize price as how much cash a buyer has to pay to get a particular worth or administration. Price can have an impact on consumer purchasing decisions and is an important component of the marketing mix. For businesses to set the right price and achieve their marketing objectives, they need to understand the factors that influence price.

C. Promotion

Promotion is one component of the advertising mix that is expected to provide data about goods or administrations to buyers and encourage them to buy. Hermawan (2016) defines promotion as any activity that expects to provide or forward an item to an objective market that fully aims to provide data about benefits, and most urgently its existence, with the desire to change judgment or empower individuals to take an action, especially those related to purchases. Promotion is an important element in marketing that can help companies achieve their marketing goals. Companies need to understand the various aspects of promotion, including objectives, influencing factors, and types of promotion, in order to design and execute effective promotional campaigns.

D. Brand Image

Brand image is the understanding that buyers have about a brand. Brand image can be formed from a variety of variables, including product quality, buyer experience, and promotions conducted by the organization. Tjiptono (2010) defines brand image as the total depiction of all affiliations associated with a brand relating to the client's beliefs about the brand. According to Rangkuti (2013), brand image is the qualities that customers associate with the brand. Brand image is an important part of promotion that can help organizations achieve their advertising goals.

Organizations need to understand the variables that influence brand image and develop techniques to create and maintain a positive brand image.

E. Purchasing Decision

Purchasing choices are the cycles undertaken by customers to decide whether to buy, what to buy, how the purchase is made, and where the purchase is made. Schiffman and Kanuk (2007) characterize buyer behavior as the activities they carry out when searching for, utilizing, assessing, and spending cash on labor and products that are expected to solve their problems. Meanwhile, according to Tjiptono (2008), purchasing decisions are a cycle in which buyers see a problem, seek information about unambiguous merchandise or brands, and evaluate how well each option can solve their problems. Purchasing choices are complex cycles that are influenced by various variables. Organizations need to understand the variables that influence buyer purchase choices in order to develop a viable promotional methodology.

F. Customer Satisfaction

Consumer loyalty is the degree of fulfillment felt by buyers after comparing their assumptions and the exhibition of the item or administration they get. Kotler and Armstrong (2012) characterize consumer loyalty as the degree of individual feeling after seeing a distinctive thing execution and a genuine thing execution. Tjiptono (2008) characterizes consumer loyalty as the degree of an individual's pleased or displeased feelings that arise after seeing the presumption and execution of the item or administration he gets. Consumer loyalty is a significant variable that organizations need to focus on. There are a number of advantages for businesses that can improve consumer satisfaction, including increased sales, market share, and consumer loyalty.

G. Research Hypothesis and Theoretical Framework

Based on previous research, we suggest a research framework that measures the framework of this study includes three main factors, namely price, promotion, and brand image, which are associated with purchasing decisions and customer satisfaction on Allchickenmart frozen food products. This research proposes seven hypotheses, which briefly state the positive influence between these variables on both purchase decisions and customer satisfaction. The hypotheses link price, promotion, brand image, purchase decision and customer satisfaction as key elements in the context of Allchickenmart frozen food products.

III. METHODS

This study uses causal examination techniques to investigate the impact of independent factors (price, promotion, brand image) on the dependent variable (purchase decision) and the mediating variable (customer loyalty). The autonomous factors in this study are price, promotion, and Brand Image, while the mediating variable is Consumer Loyalty, and the dependent variable is Purchase Choice. Various information was obtained through a survey with a Likert scale. This study utilizes

clear fact investigation, validity test, dependability test, and Partial Least Square (PLS) examination strategy to test the estimation model (external model). Testing the estimation model incorporates looking at external stacking prices, combined legitimacy, discriminant legitimacy, Normal Change Removed (AVE), as well as composite dependability and Cronbach Alpha. This research trial involved 125 frozen food customers at Allchickenmart Cilangkap, East Jakarta. The quality of respondents can be seen in Table 1.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Results

➤ Convergent validity

The loading factor value is used to test item reliability (validity indicators) for Convergent Validity. The stacking factor is a number that shows the relationship between the question score and the pointer scores that make it up. A stacking factor value greater than 0.7 is considered valid. Notwithstanding, as indicated by Hair et al. (1998) for the underlying assessment network a stacking factor of roughly 0.3 is considered to have met the basic level, and for stacking elements around 0.4 it is considered better, and for stacking factors more prominent than 0.5 it is for the most part considered critical. In this review, the limit of the buildup factor utilized is 0.7. From the consequences of

handling the information with SmartPLS displayed in Table 2, that most of the markers on each variable in this study have loading factor values greater than 0.70 and are considered valid.

➤ Discriminant Validity

The crossloading values of construct measurements are examined for discriminant validity. The degree of correlation that exists between each construct, its indicators, and indicators from other block constructs is depicted by the crossloading values. An estimated model has high discriminant validity if the relationship between the construct and its indicator is higher than the relationship with the indicator of other block constructs. Table 3 displays the crossloading results after SmartPLS 4.0 data processing. Examination of the cross loading in Table 3 shows that the value of the relationship between the development and the marker is higher than the relationship with different blocks, which indicates that all blocks or idle factors have great discriminant validity. The correlations between constructs and the root AVE values were compared for further evaluation. The recommendation states that if the square root of AVE for each construct is greater than the correlations between constructs, then the model has better discriminant validity. All construct AVE values, which ranged from 0.888 to 0.936, met the requirements, with a minimum cutoff of 0.50, in accordance with the findings.

Table 1: Characteristics of respondents

No	Indikator	Uraian	Frekuensi (Orang)	Presentase (%)
1	Jenis Kelamin	Perempuan	91	73%
		Laki-laki	34	27%
		Total	125	100%
2	Usia	< 20 Tahun	3	2%
		21 - 30	65	52%
		31 - 40	50	40%
		41 - 50	8	6%
		> 50 Tahun	-	0%
		Total	125	100%
3	Pendidikan Terakhir	SLTP	1	1%
		SLTA	49	39%
		D3	25	20%
		S1	38	30%
		S2	13	10%
		Lainnya	-	0%
		Total	125	100%
4	Pekerjaan	Karyawan Swasta	38	30%
		Mahasiswa/Pelajar	13	10%
		Wirausaha	38	30%
		PNS	25	20%
		Lainnya	13	10%
		Total	125	100%
5	Pendapatan	< Rp. 1.499.000	3	2%
		1.500.000 - 2.499.000	13	10%
		2.500.000 - 4.999.000	63	50%
		5.000.000 - 9.999.000	39	31%
		> Rp. 10.000.000	9	7%
		Total	125	100%

Table 2: Factor Loading Value

Variabel	Indikator	Outer Loading
Citra Merk	CM01	0,976
	CM02	0,896
	CM03	0,966
	CM04	0,976
	CM05	0,926
	CM06	0,928
	CM07	0,940
	CM08	0,967
Harga	HR01	0,994
	HR02	0,988
	HR03	0,972
	HR04	0,960
	HR05	0,898
	HR06	0,983
	HR07	0,886
	HR08	0,960
Keputusan Pembelian	KPB01	0,923
	KPB02	0,989
	KPB03	0,975
	KPB04	0,944
	KPB05	0,876
Kepuasan Pelanggan	KPG01	0,973
	KPG02	0,944
	KPG03	0,975
	KPG04	0,907
Promosi	PR01	0,993
	PR02	0,966
	PR03	0,960
	PR04	0,985
	PR05	0,978
	PR06	0,994
	PR07	0,928
	PR08	0,935

Table 3: Cross Loading Value

Indikator	Citra Merk	Harga	Kepuasan Pelanggan	Keputusan Pembelian	Promosi
CM01	0,976	0,971	0,973	0,973	0,383
CM02	0,896	0,890	0,865	0,914	0,319
CM03	0,966	0,966	0,946	0,950	0,385
CM04	0,976	0,978	0,973	0,982	0,389
CM05	0,926	0,870	0,887	0,862	0,496
CM06	0,928	0,882	0,883	0,858	0,482
CM07	0,940	0,910	0,953	0,916	0,429
CM08	0,967	0,968	0,949	0,946	0,370
HR01	0,983	0,994	0,978	0,989	0,377
HR02	0,971	0,988	0,976	0,989	0,365
HR03	0,956	0,972	0,963	0,975	0,358
HR04	0,928	0,960	0,919	0,944	0,351
HR05	0,833	0,898	0,828	0,851	0,296
HR06	0,974	0,983	0,972	0,975	0,363
HR07	0,908	0,886	0,881	0,872	0,458
HR08	0,950	0,960	0,927	0,933	0,366
KPB01	0,905	0,890	0,875	0,923	0,336
KPB02	0,971	0,988	0,976	0,989	0,365
KPB03	0,956	0,972	0,963	0,975	0,358
KPB04	0,928	0,960	0,919	0,944	0,351
KPB05	0,842	0,826	0,907	0,876	0,373
KPG01	0,976	0,971	0,973	0,973	0,383
KPG02	0,925	0,917	0,944	0,911	0,389
KPG03	0,981	0,984	0,975	0,982	0,386
KPG04	0,842	0,826	0,907	0,876	0,373
PR01	0,407	0,357	0,383	0,358	0,993
PR02	0,386	0,338	0,358	0,327	0,966
PR03	0,442	0,405	0,420	0,402	0,960
PR04	0,419	0,380	0,402	0,379	0,985
PR05	0,446	0,402	0,421	0,401	0,978
PR06	0,440	0,393	0,414	0,391	0,994
PR07	0,365	0,322	0,353	0,328	0,928
PR08	0,392	0,359	0,351	0,324	0,935

Table 4: AVE Value and Square Root of AVE

Variabel	Average variance extracted (AVE)
Citra Merek	0,897
Harga	0,914
Kepuasan Pelanggan	0,903
Keputusan Pembelian	0,888
Promosi	0,936

V. HYPOTHESIS TESTING RESULTS

The first hypothesis, which tested the positive relationship between brand image and customer satisfaction, yielded significant results. This variable provided reliable results during the unwavering quality test stage, confirming the recognition of the underlying speculation. This confirms that brand image affects buyer constancy. Meanwhile, interesting results were also obtained from the next hypothesis, which tested the positive influence of brand image on purchase preference. The beta coefficient of Brand Image on Purchase Decision is 0.295, with a t-statistic of 2.958. This investigation shows the significance of the t-estimate (>1.96) and p-value <0.05, which confirms the acceptance of the additional hypothesis. Furthermore, it has been shown that brand image clearly influences purchase choice.

The third hypothesis, which tested the consequences of the constructive result of price on customer loyalty, showed irrelevant results. The poor quality test results at this stage indicate variable uncertainty, so the third speculation cannot be perceived. This finding recommends that cost does not affect customer loyalty. For the time being, the Fourth hypothesis, which looks at the productive results of cost on purchase choice, yields a beta coefficient of 0.703, with a t-estimate of 7.043. With a baseline t-statistic (>1.96) and p-value <0.05, the Fourth Speculation

is accepted. Thus, it has been shown that cost clearly affects purchase choice.

The fifth hypothesis, which examines whether promotion decisively affects customer loyalty, observes that there is no remarkable impact. The assessment at the unwavering quality test stage showed disbelief in the variable, so the fifth hypothesis could not be accepted. Furthermore, it tends to be concluded that promotion does not affect customer loyalty in a meaningful way. Meanwhile, the sixth hypothesis, which analyzed the positive impact of promotion on purchase decisions, also obtained comparative results. The test showed an insignificant impact, and this variable did not gain reliance on the unwavering quality test stage. As a result, the 6th hypothesis was rejected, indicating that promotion does not influence purchasing decisions.

The seventh hypothesis, which tests whether purchase decisions decisively influence customer loyalty, yields the observation that there is a large impact. The beta coefficient value of Purchase Choice on customer loyalty is 0.703, with a t-statistic of 5.431, which indicates factual importance (t-statistic > 1.96 with p-value < 0.05). Thus, the seventh speculation is acceptable. This result shows that purchasing decisions are proven to significantly influence customer loyalty.

Fig. 1: Research Model Results

Table 5: Path Coefficient Results Path Coefficient Results

Hipotesis	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
Citra Merek -> Kepuasan Pelanggan	0,476	0,471	0,141	3,369	0,001
Citra Merek -> Keputusan Pembelian	0,295	0,304	0,100	2,958	0,004
Harga -> Kepuasan Pelanggan	-0,187	-0,193	0,166	1,130	0,261
Harga -> Keputusan Pembelian	0,703	0,694	0,100	7,043	0,000
Keputusan Pembelian -> Kepuasan Pelanggan	0,703	0,714	0,129	5,431	0,000
Promosi -> Kepuasan Pelanggan	0,005	0,005	0,019	0,273	0,785
Promosi -> Keputusan Pembelian	-0,018	-0,016	0,016	1,083	0,281

VI. DISCUSSION

The results show that Brand Image essentially influences purchase choices, which is supported by the positive and large beta coefficients. The constructive result of Brand Image on consumer loyalty is supported by the test results, which show its importance. This finding is consistent with the perspective of Fahimah et al. (2022), who found that brand image fundamentally affects consumer loyalty, which is influenced by elements such as strength, uniqueness, and tendency.

Price has an effect on buying choices. This finding is in accordance with the assessment of Lestari et al. (2021) which reveals that cost basically affects buying choices, because cost is a determining component for customers in determining buying choices. Price has no effect on consumer loyalty, as seen from the experimental results which show insignificance.

In accordance with the findings, the test results show that Promotion does not have a significant positive effect on Purchasing Decisions. Ardiansyah et al., (2022) state that basically, promotion does not influence purchasing choices, because this variable cannot persuade buyers strongly enough to make a purchase. The notion of advancement, for this situation, is characterized as a showcasing strategy geared toward giving data to potential buyers with respect to the message or value contained in an item or brand, yet research findings show that advancement does not essentially convince buyers to make a purchase or use. Therefore, the consequences of this research support the view that advancements limitedly influence customers' purchasing choices, which has significant consequences for showcasing methodologies. Advancements also do not

clearly influence consumer loyalty, as the experimental results show the insignificance of this variable. This finding is not the same as the research of Kurniasih et al. (2022), which states that transaction advancements, such as limits, coupons, and extraordinary occasions with attractive offers, noticeably affect consumer loyalty. Therefore, the consequences of this study indicate the need for additional assessments regarding specific techniques to attract buyer interest and form consumer loyalty.

Buying choices significantly affect consumer loyalty. This finding is in accordance with the testing of Suyatmi et al., (2019), which reveals that Purchasing Options affect the level of consumer loyalty. The results of this discussion show that Price and Brand Image have an influence on Purchasing Decisions. Meanwhile, Progress does not show a massive impact on Consumer loyalty or Purchase Choice.

VII. CONCLUSION

The results of this study indicate that Brand Image and Price have a positive impact on Purchasing Decisions. In contrast, Promotion has no significant effect on Customer Satisfaction or Purchasing Decisions. Finally, Purchasing Decision has a positive influence on Customer Satisfaction.

Further research, Thisdata is a good starting point, but further research may be needed to explore these factors further, as well as consider other variables that may have an influence. With more in-depth research, companies can gain more detailed insights to direct their marketing strategies.

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